

ISic0830

I.Sicily inscription 0830

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building (?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found near the temple of Olympian Zeus

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Ε]πικράτης Ἀ[γ]έα υἱ[ὸς]
2. ΑΤΟΔΥΜΑΣ οἰκοδ
3. ομήσας πέλεθρον
4. τοῖς αὐτοῦ υἱ[ι]έεσσι
5. ἔδωκε τᾶι πόλ[ει]

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492455

EDCS 39101981

PHI 140301

Bibliography

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